

WHAT IS THE PROCRASTINATION? THE CAUSES OF PROCRASTINATION.

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Annotation: procrastinating. In this article, we will see the reasons. Have you ever put off your homework till the last minute? Maybe delayed writing an essay till the last possible hour? All of us are guilty of delaying tasks and putting off important work. This is essentially of this problem.

Key words: Procrastination, procrastinator, causes, excuses.

As it will be seen in this procrastination article, this is not a rare phenomenon. Almost everybody is guilty of it at some point in their lives. So we question ourselves the question - why do we procrastinate even when we are very busy most of the time?

At the moment, we will focus on some causes of it. There are some main reasons of procrastination are surrounding circumstance, the work is not much important for procrastinator or the extend of work is so huge.

What do I mean by surrounding circumstance, first of all, social media (telegram, instagram and others). For example: You start doing your homework from English and at the moment you do not know a word and process to search it on the internet, then you can see one of the best friend of yours sent a message to you and you would like to chat with her/him. And you spend at least an hour for it then you remember why I had to use the internet however one hour has already passed away.... Secondly, if the people around you who delay their work also influence you whether you want it or not.

Next one, you are likely to see a video (that is about someone's big achievements or how can we develop ourselves) which can absolutely motivate you. And you will be motivated from it and begin making very huge schedule for you, but then you are afraid of the plan you have made because of its dimension. You can follow your schedule at least a week then you may find unworthy excuses very easily. Finally, everything you planned has been broken down.

And also, there are some universal reasons that cause people to delay their tasks and their actions. One of them is the fear of failure. When a person delays doing important task or disinterested in finishing it, the cause could be a deep-rooted fear of failure. It is in human nature to avoid and fear failure. So by choosing to never finish the task, we can avoid the consequences as well.

Another reason is the lack of focus and determination. Feeling directionless and unfocused can often cause people to lose their wills to do their jobs. This leads to procrastination. Sometimes the lack of goals and objectives is also the reason a person loses their focus. Since they do not have an end-goal in mind, they end up wasting energy in other useless tasks.

There are other reasons a person may procrastinate. Sometimes a person may be too much of a perfectionist. This distracts them from other tasks. And then there are other reasons like laziness, low energy level, easy distractions, etc.

In conclusion, We can say, every problem has a solution when it comes to procrastination, it also has a solution but how? The simple solution is just try by heart!

References:

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